

Fig. S4. Serum titers of anti-mBSA antibodies from LAP-treated mice on antigen-induced-arthritis (AIA). mBSA-immunized C57BL/6 mice were treated orally with LAP (10 mg/kg) or vehicle every day from 12-21 day after first immunization. The graph shows the anti-mBSA IgG levels in the serum from naive and mBSA-immunized mice treated or not with LAP on day 21.